

An Arduino Based Digital Data Generating System for Surface Electrodes Switching in A 32-Electrode Electrical Impedance Tomography (EIT) Data Collection

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ABSTRACT

Electrical Impedance Tomography (EIT) is a computerized non-invasive imaging technique which reconstructs impedance distributions within a domain under test (DUT) from the impedance data recorded by injecting an alternating current of small magnitude into the DUT and measuring the generated voltage with the help of electrodes fitted to the DUT. Thus, EIT has its vast application in medical fields for imaging of human tissues or organs. An EIT system hardware has four main parts, namely, Constant Current Injector (CCI), Signal Conditioner Block (SCB), Data Acquisition System (DAS) and Electrode Switching Module (ESM).. The CCI injects a constant amplitude of alternating current signal and the DAS measures the developed boundary potential data from the surface electrodes switched by ESM. In this paper, an Electrode Switching Module (ESM) for a 32 electrode EIT system has been built. For four probe impedance measurement (i.e. two current and two voltage electrodes), four 32:1 multiplexers are being used for selecting four electrodes at a time. The ESM is operated using an Arduino Uno. Four 32:1 MUXs, two of which is used for evaluating current and the other two for evaluating voltage difference.

KEYWORDS: EIT, DUT, ESM, MUXs

1. INTRODUCTION

Electrical Impedance Tomography or EIT [1-9] is a non-invasive imaging method used for modelling or imaging of any domain under test (DUT) with the help of conductivity, permittivity and impedance measured by electrodes connected around the DUT. EIT is widely used because there is no need for sectioning the DUT which is to be inspected. Moreover, in medical applications, it has an edge over other conventional methods because it does not have health hazards like radiation of X-Rays or CT scans or Strong Magnetic Fields of MRI or high intensity sounds like Ultrasonography [10-18]. But it also has some disadvantages like low spatial resolution compared to other conventional methods, noise sensitivity and contact impedance variation between boundary and electrode. It also has limited penetration capability. The measurement calculating equations are also having high non-linearity and they are also highly ill-posed in nature. In recent times, EIT has been used in many fields including the biomedical and medical applications [19-23]

2. INSTRUMENTATION

Figure 1. A 32-Electrode Electrical Impedance Tomography (EIT) System Schematic

In EIT system the electronic hardware is developed with a constant current injector, signal processing circuit, electrode switching module and the data acquisition system [24-28]. In EIT technology, a low frequency low amplitude alternating electrical current (or voltage) signal is applied at the boundary of a domain under test (DUT) and the developed voltage (or current) signals are measured at the boundary using an array of surface electrodes attached to the DUT. The boundary voltage-current data are fed to an image reconstruction algorithm (a computer program) which reconstructs the spatial distribution of the domain conductivity or resistivity from the boundary data measured. For measuring the boundary voltage current data, four probe impedance measurement is used in EIT, where two of them are used for injecting current and the other two are used for measuring voltages around different surfaces of the DUT. Then these measured voltages are used in various algorithms to find out the probable conductivity distribution of the DUT, imaging the object electrically. But we cannot connect only four probes with four electrodes as it will not generate sufficient data for the algorithms to collect data properly. Generally, 16 electrodes are used of their balance between spatial resolution and practicality. However, higher number of electrodes can be used to get a better spatial resolution. So, a 32:1 Multiplexer is used in this development for a better resolution.

3. DATA COLLECTION & IMAGE RECONSTRUCTION

Data collection is done through the electrodes placed on the periphery of the DUT by sequentially activating pair of current electrode and then measuring with the voltage difference between two voltage electrode (4 electrode method) or one voltage electrode and ground (2 electrode method) also sequentially for the rest electrodes while keeping two current electrodes fixed. The electrodes are placed uniformly around the DUT for comprehensive data.

Based on the method of selecting current electrodes, EIT methods can be separated into two – 1. Neighbouring or Adjacent Current Injection Method and 2. Opposite Current Injection Method. In Adjacent Current Injection Method two current electrodes are selected in such a way that they are adjacent to one another while the voltage across rest are measured in a similar way. But in Opposite Current Injection Method, the electrode pairs are opposite to one another.

After collection of data, an image is constructed using the measured data with the help of suitable software like MATLAB.

4. STRUCTURE OF THE ELECTRODE SWITCHING MODULE

To inject the currents through the electrodes and to measure the potential between two electrodes, a specific module is required to select the electrodes as desired and connect it to the two current probes and two voltage probes. The module responsible for switching electrodes is known as the Electrode Switching Module (ESM).

A prototype is made using Veroboard, ribbon wires, jumpers, MUXs, LEDs and 1K resistors for limiting the current passing through the LEDs. The number of the inputs of each MUX must be equal to the number of electrodes present in the EIT system, so in a 32-electrode system a 32:1 MUXs are required. Four 32:1 MUXs are required to select 4 electrodes at a time. Each 32:1 MUX is made by cascading two 16-channel MUXs labelled 'A' and 'B'. Here, 32 electrodes are replaced by 32 LEDs and one 1K current limiting resistor is connected in series with each of the LEDs. The LEDs are placed in a circular manner on the Veroboard and are numbered from 1 to 32. The positive pin of each LED is connected to a 1K resistor. The other ends of the 32 resistors are connected to 1st to 32nd pin of the 'connector pins (i)' respectively. The connector pins (i) and the connector pins (ii) are connected together with the help of removable jumpers as shown in the figure. When one electrode is selected, the corresponding LED glows. A connector pin is used to join the 32 LEDs and the 32 outputs of the MUX so that the dummy electrodes i.e. LEDs can be removed and later connected with the actual electrodes. The Set A consists the numbers from 1 to 16 which are the digital pins of 00000 to 01111 and are connected to the LED set of 1 to 16, the next MUX is passed through the NOT gate and the set B consists

of power pin numbers from 17 to 32 which are the digital pins of 10000 to 11111. The MUX also consists of an inhibitor which when switched off makes the MUX to function otherwise it is terminated. Thus, the inhibitor regulates the functioning of the MUX pairs. The four MUX pairs are divided into two sets consisting of voltage and current arranged in a horizontal fashion. There are four 32:1 MUXs namely V1, V2, I1, I2. Each of the 32:1 MUX consists of two 16:1 MUXs (CD4067BE) namely A and B which are cascaded together. The MUXs V1 and V2 are used for calculating the voltage differences across each pair of the 32 electrodes (i.e., LED points), the I1 and I2 perform the function of injecting current to each pair of the electrodes. The four select lines namely A, B, C, D along with the inhibit form the five select lines as mentioned above. The inhibit acts as the MSB and the select line A as the LSB.

Figure 2. 32:1 Multiplexer IC (a) CD4067BE DIP IC from Texas Instruments Inc. (USA), (b) The pin diagram of the CD4067BE DIP IC from Texas Instruments Inc. (USA)

5. DETAILED WORKING OF THE ELECTRODE SWITCHING MODULE (ESM)

The inputs are passed through the Arduino where a program is being run and the supply is provided through the 5V power supply. Two of the cascaded MUX pairs namely I1 and I2 are connected using an adder series of circuits together in the outer loop where they are used to evaluate the current. The other two pairs of V1 and V2 is being run in the inner loop to get the desired value. The working of the two cascaded MUXs are as follows:

Figure 3. The schematic of the electrode switching module (ESM) for a 32-electrode EIT system using cascaded 16:1 Multiplexers.

The V_{cc} pins of all the IC CD4067BE's are shorted together and connected to the positive side of the central connector pin. The supply of the hex inverter is also provided by this pin. The ground pins of all the pair of MUXs, the hex inverter and the LEDs are connected to the central ground pin. The common output pins of MUX A and MUX B for each of the four cascaded pairs are shorted and connected to their respective connector pins marked as I_1, I_2, V_1, V_2 . An external 5V DC supply is provided across the central positive and ground pins. The connector pins I_1, I_2, V_1, V_2 are also fed to the supply. Four sets of connector pins containing 5 pins each are fitted into the Veroboard which serve as the select lines for the four 32:1 MUXs.

All the digital pins numbered as 1st to 32nd of MUX V1 are connected to 1st to 32nd pin of 'connector pins (ii)' respectively. as shown in figure. The digital pin 1 of MUX V1 is connected to the digital pin1 of all the other three MUXs. Similarly, every other digital pins i.e., from 2 to 32 are connected in the same fashion. The connector pins (i) and the connector pins (ii) are used instead of shorting the LEDs directly with the digital pins of any of the MUXs so that the connector pins (i) can be replaced by electrodes whenever necessary.

The selection of electrodes i.e., LEDs functioning can be done in two methods namely: 3 electrode and 4-electrode method.

For 3-electrode method, we only need 1 adder circuit. Two binary counters are generated using a nested loop so that for each state of first counter, the next counter will count from 00000 to 11111. The first counter is taken as the control input for first current electrode I_1 and it is also passed through an adder circuit adding just 1 bit in the LSB position for selecting the exact next electrode and connect it to the control input of second current electrode I_2 . For example, if the control input of I_1 is 00000, the adder adds 00001 to it, making the output of the adder 00001 which is fed into the control input of I_2 , selecting 1st and 2nd electrode. The first voltage electrode V_1 is given the second binary counter as control input, so for selection of each pair of current electrodes, the voltage is selected sequentially 32 times. The second voltage electrode V_2 is grounded for the 3-electrode method.

For the 4-electrode method, the same algorithm is followed except for the addition of the voltage electrode. The control input of V_1 passed through an adder and increased by 1 bit in the LSB and fed into the controlling input of V_2 , selecting exactly next electrode of V_1 . In this method, differential voltage is measured between two adjacent electrodes, terminating the common mode noise.

The adder circuit configuration and connections are defined below:

Cascading two 4-bit adder can enable us to add two numbers comprising of 8 bits. But as only five bits are needed, the first five bits are used from LSB and rest are grounded. So, the maximum number we are feeding to the adder must be 00011111. In the first 7483 IC, we are using 2 sets of input i.e. A_0, A_1, A_2, A_3 and B_0, B_1, B_2, B_3 and outputs S_0, S_1, S_2, S_3 and carry-out, we use the carry out of the first adder IC and connect it to the second IC's carry in. The Second IC's A_0 and B_0 serves as MSB to the 5-bit input and S_0 as the MSB of the output. Rest of the inputs of second adder are grounded. The carry-in of the first adder is also grounded. The LSB of the second one of the two cascaded adder ICs serves as the MSB of the entire 5-bit adder circuit and the other four bit are taken from the first one. We require a total of three adder circuits i.e., six adder IC two of each cascaded together to form the entire setup. The first set of select lines gets directly connected to the I_1 and the adder circuit 1 adds 1 to the LSB in the outer loop, which is identified as I_2 . This result from the adder circuit is drawn to the next adder circuit where 1 is again added to the LSB which forms the start of the inner loop i.e., V_1 and this adder runs in the way that mathematically it is always two bits ahead of the initial loop. Again, in the same process 1 is added in the LSB in the second pin of the inner loop i.e., V_2 and the total nested loop configuration is tied together by this method.

Figure 4. (a) Front side of the ESM Module after connecting wire, (b) Back side of the ESM Module after connecting wires.

6. ARDUINO IDE BASED AUTOMATIC ELECTRODE SWITCHING MODULE

The Arduino IDE is also interfaced with phantom or subject with surface electrode array through the ESM. The Arduino IDE is developed to perform two works in EIT: digital data generation for operating the analog multiplexers of the ESM and analog voltage signal measurement. The Arduino IDE developed sequentially generates a 16-bit digital data required for the operating the analog multiplexers of the ESM to switch the current and voltage electrodes attached on phantom or subject under test. For a particular current pattern the Arduino IDE collects the voltage data from the electrodes connected to the voltage measuring channels (called voltage electrodes). The current injection through the Current input power pin results in the Electrode switching by ESM and voltage measurements by Arduino IDE all are controlled by Arduino Uno and the applied program.

Figure 5. Pinout of ARDUINO Board and ATmega328PU microcontroller [Picture Courtesy: <https://www.circuito.io/blog/arduino-uno-pinout/>]

7. DIFFERENT STAGES OF ESM UNDER RUNNING CONDITION, CONTROLLED BY ARDUINO

The PCB boards of the electrode switching module (ESM) is developed for a 32-electrode EIT system using cascaded 16:1 Multiplexers. The ESM PCB board is tested using LED logics. The following figure shows the experimental setup for electrode switching sequences obtained for a four-electrode method based EIT data collection procedure where two current electrodes and two voltage electrodes are used simultaneously to get the boundary voltage-current data. The boundary voltage-current data are collected and stored in PC for the EIT image reconstruction.

Figure 6. PCB boards of the electrode switching module (ESM) for a 32-electrode EIT system using cascaded 16:1 Multiplexers.

8. CONCLUSIONS

An arduino based digital data generating system is developed for surface electrodes switching in a 32-electrode electrical impedance tomography (EIT) data collection. The developed ESM (Electrode Switching Module) is tested with the digital data generated from the Arduino UNO. The digital data sequences generated by Arduino UNO are tested with LED logics in breadboard. Arduino UNO generated digital data are found suitable for multiplexer operation. The 32:1 multiplexers are operated with digital data and the efficient electrode switching is observed. The developed ESM is found suitable for acquiring the boundary data the real object such as practical phantoms.

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